

TrustedCI Fellow Experience Report

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This report summarizes Phuong Cao's valuable experience in participating with the TrustedCI PIs, past fellows, and community members in 2023 [1].

Background. As a cybersecurity research specialist at NCSA [2], Phuong has been involved in research of novel attack detection methods and the development/deployment of security techniques such as honeypots, virtual machine monitors, and token-based authentication. He has worked with many capable security-minded colleagues from NCSA and peer institutions such as Indiana University, San Diego Supercomputing Center, and Berkeley Lab. Learned about NSF's TrustedCI program, Phuong applied for and was accepted to the TrustedCI Fellows program, in 2023.

Experiences. The TrustedCI program has brought significant growth to Phuong, not only in terms of technical security domain knowledge and policies but also in developing a long-term research agenda to secure cyberinfrastructure, particularly in the High-Performance Computing area. Through feedback and discussion with TrustedCI leadership, he has been awarded the first seed grant as the PI to study formal verification of token-based authentication [3] – which he plans to collaborate more closely with the TrustedCI community once completing a prototype. Phuong ongoing research on honeypot design, attack preemption, resiliency characterization of supercomputers (with IBM), and securing FABRIC testbed also benefits greatly from interacting with TrustedCI community members at the NSF Cybersecurity Summit at Berkeley Lab, contributing in several publications [4, 5] and a tutorial on security log analyses [6]. Most importantly, Phuong has been able to establish new collaborations with senior fellows at ESNET and SDSC to address the security of Jupyter Notebooks, which is an urgent problem that TrustedCI can help. The existing TrustedCI threat model and framework also proved very helpful in formally analyzing adversaries and conforming to various NSF programs' calls for proposals.

Conclusion. The author would like to thank the support of NCSA, NSF, the TrustedCI leadership team (Jim Basney and Sean Peisert), other fellows, and community members. I look forward to meaningful collaboration in the future.

References

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